

HOW EUPHEMISMS FORMED

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With its clear anthropocentric orientation, the new scientific paradigm focused on the study of euphemisms not only as a form of communication but also as a cultural unit, influencing not only linguistic but also extralinguistic factors influencing the emergence and functioning of euphemisms.

The different classifications of euphemistic methods available in the linguistic literature differ in the criteria for grouping. Classifications of euphemistic methods can be conditionally divided into three groups. The growing interest in the phenomenon of euphemism in the literature and journalism of the XXI century makes it necessary to study the multifaceted phenomenon of euphemism, to seek a new complex approach to the interpretation of connotative information embodied in euphemism by linguistic means. The use of euphemisms is often associated with a taboo phenomenon. Taboo is a representative of the national spirit, one of the mirrors. Taboo emerged as the oldest unwritten law of mankind through prohibitions. The word taboo comes from the Tongan language of Polynesia, meaning "to forbid, to forbid." The purpose of taboo is to remove the word-name from consumption, not the concept that society needs. Thus the taboo mechanism is defined by replacing a word with another word or changing its name. A word or phrase that replaces a taboo word is a euphemism.

According to Rawson :

Euphemism is mild agreeable or round about word used in place of coarse , painful or offensive one"

Neman and Silver claim that euphemism is a way to substitute an offensive or unpleasant word for a more explicit , offensive one, thereby veneration the truth by using polite words.

L.P. Krysin in his work "Euphemisms in the modern Russian language" identified three main functions of the use of euphemisms:

1. Softening a word that sounds rude and unpleasant to the listener
2. Truth-covering, camouflage
3. Hiding the truth.

The most effective methods of forming euphemisms in English can be presented in an analyzed and generalized form as follows:

1. Semantic shift

growth for cancer

Extra-curricular activity for adultery

2. Understatement

sleep for die

not bright for fool

3. Indirection

Too touchy topics and terms maybe alluded to in various ways by mentioning one aspect of the subject , circumstance involving it , or a related subject ; for example:

an assembly center is an indirect euphemism for *prison*

Soldiers break off contact with the enemy which means *they retreat*

4. External Borrowing

Most taboo words are usually rendered in French or Latin ; such as

affaire or *amour* are euphemisms for *love*

sortie and *trage* for *war*

brassiere or *lingerie* for *women`s underwear*

halitosis from the Latin *halitus* meaning *bad breath*

5. Internal Borrowing

Euphemisms can also form different sublanguages such as, jargons or technical terms, for instance, a disease such as syphilis can be made less offensive by using technical jargon as *treponemal disease* or *luetic disease*

6. Metaphorical Transfer

This procedure is a comparison of things of one order to things of another such as a comparison of one flower to another variety. Therefore, the word pimple is euphemized as blossom.

7. Reduplication

Reduplication is a repetition of a syllable, letter or a word possibly with modification of one of the repetitions such as *jeepers creepers* which is euphemized as *Jesus Christ*.

8. Blending

Most blending words made by joining two words or more to create a new one such as

strewth which means *God`s wrath*

zounds as *God`s wounds*

drat as *God`s rot*

9. Phonological Distortion

"The sound of words can be altered to conceal something that is offensive." (Allan and Burridge, 1991:2).

Euphemisms can be created when the speakers intentionally distort the pronunciation of words, such as *crumbs*, *crust* or *cripes* for Christ.

The same case with the word *hell* which is euphemized as *heck*.

10. Omission

This involves leaving out the letters of taboo words after the initial, such as S--- instead of *Shit*.

11. Diminutive

This procedure is the formation of new terms by shortening a name and adding a suffix to indicate affection or smallness such as the word

buttocks is euphemized as *heinie* which is the diminutive of *hindend*.

12. Circumlocution

Using longer expressions is called circumlocution. Euphemisms which have more letters and syllables are deployed in place of a single one, such as

A Middle Eastern dancing sounds better than *belly dance*

Solid human waste is a euphemism of *faeces*

13. Clipping

Clipping is the deletion of some part of a longer to give a shorter word with the same meaning; as in,

nation for *damnation*

bra for *brassiere*

jeeze for *Jesus Christ*

14. Back Formation

The backformation of words refer to the substitution of one part of speech with a shortened form for another; for example,

burgle is derived from *burglar* and is a euphemism for *rob*

15. Apocopation

This process can be defined as the way to shorten or omit the last syllable of a word, such as

Vamp for *Vampire*

Lav for *lavatory*

16. Abbreviation

Words which may create dismay if used in public are acceptable when shortened to their initial letters; for example,

B.S for *bullshit*

T.S for *transsexual*

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, euphemisms have clear functional characteristics: they are used in situations and contexts where the language is in action, their understanding of moral and ethical values dictates the need to replace direct nominations with indirect ones. People can learn a lot about a society, its knowledge, culture and values, simply by studying euphemism. Therefore, it is really important to go through the history of euphemism.

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